

COMPOSITION OF PRUSSIAN AND TURNBULL'S BLUES. PART IV. STUDY OF THEIR ADSORPTIVE PROPERTIES.

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Studies on the adsorption of ferrocyanogen and ferric radicals by Prussian blue, and of ferrous and ferricyanogen radicals by Turnbull's blue have been carried out. Evidence has been produced to show that in some cases chemical action and in some cases negative adsorption may take place.

In a previous paper (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 213, 240) the analytical results of various samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues, prepared by mixing the reactants in different proportions and concentrations, have produced evidence of the possibility of adsorption of different groups or radicals in course of precipitation. A detailed study of the phenomenon has, therefore, been carried out by a series of experiments and their results discussed in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Solutions of ferric chloride and potassium ferrocyanide of known strengths were mixed together in equivalent proportion to precipitate a calculated amount of Prussian blue. The precipitate was thoroughly washed free from electrolytes and suspended in boiled distilled water, the total volume being made up to a litre. The precipitate was then vigorously shaken to make the suspension uniform as far as possible, before using the suspension for adsorption experiments. 10 C.c. of this suspension were quickly withdrawn and transferred into several flasks arranged in succession. Gradually increasing amounts of the salt, whose adsorption had to be determined, were added to the blue precipitate and the total volume of the mixture was made up to 100 c.c. in each case, and left overnight to settle. If on adding the salt solution the blue precipitate assumed a colloidal form, about 2 to 3 g. of ammonium chloride were added to coagulate it, and then the equilibrium concentration was determined by withdrawing 5 to 10 c.c. of the clear supernatant solution.

For Turnbull's blue the same procedure was adopted.

The equilibrium concentration of ferric chloride was estimated gravimetrically as Fe_2O_3 ; those of ferrous sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide were determined by titrating against $N/200\text{-KMnO}_4$ solution; while that of potassium ferricyanide was estimated by iodometry where the liberated iodine from potassium iodide was titrated against $N/200\text{-sodium thiosulphate}$ solution.

On the basis of these estimations the adsorptive properties of various samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues have been studied. In some cases negative adsorption has also been observed. By extrapolation it has been possible, further, to observe some cases of adsorption which are followed by chemical changes, after a certain amount of the adsorbent had been added to the Prussian or Turnbull's blue.

DISCUSSION.

From the curves it follows apparently that some samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues at first display a tendency of adsorption which is later disturbed by the effects of chemical reaction between the adsorbent and the adsorbate.

FIG. 1.

Curves I and II refer respectively to P. blues obtained by mixing (i) FeCl_3 and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ in equiv. proportion and (ii) 1 equiv. of FeCl_3 with $3/2$ equiv. of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.

FIG. 2 (Curve III).

Curve III refers to P. blue prepared as in Curve II, Fig. 2.

Curves I, II, VIII and X lend support to the view that adsorption and chemical oxidation-reduction are both responsible for the final composition of Prussian and Turnbull's blues; hence the percentage composition of the various samples vary considerably with the proportion and concentration of the reactants mixed together as communicated in a previous publication (*loc. cit.*).

FIG. 3.

 $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ adsorbed by 1 g. of P. blue.

Curves IV-VI refer respectively to P. blue prepared by mixing $FeCl_3$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in (i) equiv. proportion, (ii) 1 : 3/2, (iii) 3/2 : 1.

FIG. 4 (Curve VII).

Excess of Fe calc. as $FeSO_4$ at equib. conc.

Curve VII refers to $FeSO_4$ added over the amount added to T. blue prepared by mixing $FeSO_4$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ in equiv. proportion.

Curve VII definitely suggests that a chemical action takes place between acidified ferrous sulphate and the precipitate of Turnbull's blue, formed by mixing the reactants in equivalent proportion. The results of adsorption experiments lend further support to the view, previously communicated, that during the precipitation of Turnbull's blue, by mixing an acidified solution of ferrous sulphate with potassium ferricyanide, the role of chemical change is much greater than adsorption. This is why a negative adsorption has been observed. The curve shows that after a certain concentration of ferrous sulphate, the limit of chemical change as well as that of adsorption has been reached. With increasing quantities of ferrous sulphate added to 10 c.c. of the suspension containing 0.1 g. of Turnbull's blue, the liberated amount of the reducing product (calculated as ferrous sulphate in excess of the amount already added) at first decreased and then became constant. It seems from the curve that the reaction between the Turnbull's blue and ferrous sulphate was complete at a concentration of 0.304 g. per litre, while the adsorption of ferrous sulphate continued to increase till the concentration reached 0.456 g. per litre. The curve, therefore, runs down a short slope between the concentration range of 0.304 to 0.456 g. of $FeSO_4$ per litre and then becomes parallel to the concentration axis.

Curve III shows that chemical action ultimately influences adsorption when gradually increasing quantities of ferric chloride are added to Prussian blue prepared by mixing 3/2 equivalents of ferric chloride with one

equivalent of potassium ferrocyanide. The negative adsorption observed in this case seems to be due to the fact that Prussian blue prepared with excess of ferric chloride retains already enough of it through adsorption, so that with further quantities of ferric chloride gradually added, the limit of adsorption is surpassed and chemical action sets in. Hence the excess of iron compound, calculated as FeCl_3 , released by Prussian blue on adding increasing amounts of ferric chloride, tends to reach a certain maximum beyond which the curve becomes almost parallel to the concentration axis of FeCl_3 .

Curve IV is an adsorption curve showing that Prussian blue prepared by mixing the reactants in equivalent proportion adsorbs increasing quantities of potassium ferrocyanide up to a certain limit on adding gradually increasing amounts of the latter. Similar results are shown by the adsorption curves V and VI where the Prussian blues have been prepared by mixing (i) one equivalent of ferric chloride with $3/2$ equivalents of potassium ferrocyanide, and (ii) $3/2$ equivalents of ferric chloride with one equivalent of potassium ferrocyanide respectively. Such observations support the formation of adsorption compounds, which depends of course, on the conditions of precipitation and formation of the blue.

It will be observed, further, that the sample of Prussian blue prepared by mixing excess ($3/2$ equivalents) of ferric chloride adsorbs more of potassium ferrocyanide than that which was prepared by mixing ferric chloride and potassium ferrocyanide in equivalent proportions. Likewise, a sample prepared by mixing $3/2$ equivalents of potassium ferrocyanide adsorbs much less of this salt than one prepared by mixing the reactants in equivalent proportions. These results are quite in conformity with the laws of adsorption.

In curve I the ferric chloride is adsorbed up to a certain concentration after which the amount adsorbed slowly decreases with increasing concentrations of ferric chloride indicating the disturbance of adsorption phenomenon by the chemical action after a certain quantity of the adsorbate has been added. Curve II leads to a similar inference. In this curve the phenomenon of adsorption goes up to a much higher concentration of ferric chloride, in as much as the sample of this blue was prepared by adding excess ($3/2$ equivalents) of potassium ferrocyanide, while the sample in curve I was prepared by mixing the reactants in equivalent proportion. These results, are in conformity with the adsorptive properties of substances.

Curve VIII shows that in Turnbull's blue, prepared by mixing the reactants in equivalent proportion, adsorption of potassium ferricyanide takes place up to a certain extent, when the chemical action starts and

goes a greater length than that of Prussian blue with ferric chloride. From curve IX it is evident that when Turnbull's blue is prepared by mixing one equivalent of ferrous sulphate with $3/2$ equivalents of potassium ferricyanide, its adsorptive capacity as well as its chemical reactivity towards the latter are almost or completely exhausted. Hence the curve is a line parallel to the equilibrium concentration axis.

FIG. 5.

Curves VIII-X refer respectively to T. blue prepared by mixing FeSO_4 and $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ as (i) 1 : 1, (ii) 1 : $3/2$, (iii) $3/2$: 1.

Curve X shows that the adsorption of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ is much greater with Turnbull's blue prepared by mixing $3/2$ equivalents of ferrous sulphate than that which had been prepared by mixing one equivalent of ferrous sulphate. This is quite usual in view of the fact that in the former sample, much greater amount of ferrous sulphate remains adsorbed than in the latter. The steep course of curve X further indicates the avidity between the adsorbed Fe and potassium ferricyanide.

While discussing the analytical results of the various samples of Prussian and Turnbull's blues in the previous communication, already referred to, the rôle of selective adsorption of Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ was observed to be very important in determining the final composition of these compounds. The adsorption curves also lead to a similar conclusion and confirm the view that Prussian blue has a much greater adsorptive power for ferric and ferrocyanogen radicals than Turnbull's blue prepared under similar conditions.

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